

ISO/TC 20/SC 14/WG8

Downstream space services and space-based applications

In today's increasingly complex space environment, it is more important than ever to ensure a better global approach for end user applications and services, and for the environment in which the space programmes operate (civil, commercial, government, academia, etc.). In this context, ISO space standards fulfil a key role in providing a global approach, by reducing duplication of effort and leveraging expertise in the associated communities.

ISO/TC20/SC14 seeks to facilitate commerce and to enhance safety, efficiency, and interoperability in all aspects of space activity by developing and achieving international consensus on standards and practices for space stakeholders.

Working Group 8 (WG8) of ISO/TC20/SC14 coordinates and develops synergies with international, regional, national organizations, and industry involved in **downstream space services and space-based applications**.

A standards framework for end user applications and services

WG8's key objective is to develop new market of space system utilization. Space systems provide a huge merit for the society and economy in each country; and space-based services contribute to people's Quality of Life (QOL) across the world. Space systems should be utilized furthermore in the industry in the future. *Downstream space services and space-based applications* cover the field depicted in the figure below, whatever the application is crewed and uncrewed.

ISO space downstream standards

The structure of ISO's TC20/SC14/WG8 is shown in the overleaf.

WG8 is then able to build standards either for **downstream space services** itself or any **downstream space-based applications** using one or more space services:

- Space service: In general any standards covering needs of a specific space service - independently from the final targeted application-, could be addressed here.
- Space-based application: In general any standards covering needs of a specific application using one or more space services could be addressed here.

WG8 is focusing on 4 space services (also named pillars):

1. PNT / GNSS, (Position, Navigation, Time / Global Navigation Satellites System)
2. Remote sensing/Earth Observation,
3. Communication using space systems,
4. Space weather downstream applications and effects

Future standards development initiatives

WG8 welcomes new participations to help, maintain and develop space downstream standards. Come and join the WG8 community:

Overview of the WG8 work program

Status as of 20th Nov. 2025

4 published (green),
 9 in development (mag. pink grey),
 7 Preliminary Work Item (white)

Legend:

Publication stage (60)	Approval stage (50)	Enquiry stage (40)	Committee stage (30)
Preparatory stage (20)	Proposal stage (10)	Preliminary stage	

18197	Space systems — Space based services requirements for centimeter class positioning
22591	Space systems — Space-based services for a high accuracy positioning system with safety requirements [Tech Spec]
24245	Space systems — Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receiver class codes
24246	Space systems — Requirements for Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) positioning augmentation centers
20550	Space systems — Pointing management for optical Earth observation
20930	Space systems — Calibration requirements for satellite-based passive microwave sensors
25082	Space systems — Assessment of GNSS-based positioning system — Part 1: Definitions and system engineering procedures for the establishment and assessment of performances
22591	Space systems — Space-based applications for a high accuracy positioning system with safety requirements
	PWI "Contemporary lunar reference system for experimental enterprises"
26335	NP "Space-based rescue services using low power wide area (LPWA) technology"
26252	NP "Interoperable spaceborne remote sensing services"
25082	NP "Space systems — Assessment of GNSS-based positioning system — Part 2"
25756	NP Space systems — Space-based positioning with optical augmentation for social and industrial infrastructures
25082	PWI "Space systems — Assessment of GNSS-based positioning system — Part 3"
	PWI "Lunar planar coordinate system"
	PWI "General requirement for GNSS performance monitoring and assessment"
13657	Space systems — Space-based services — Positioning information exchange service
	PWI Space Weather vocabulary for downstream enterprise
	PWI GNSS timing receivers - requirement and verifications
16215	Space systems — Space-based positioning, navigation and timing (PNT) services — Part 1: Architectural basis

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